

THE INTELLIGENT PROCESSING OF LAMINATED COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

In this work, a strategy for controlling the cure cycle of composites during the fabrication process has been developed. This approach couples direct measurements of composite properties with models of the cure process for decision making purposes. A high temperature ultrasonic transducer is used to characterize the changes in the properties of the polymer matrix during cure. Particular attention is focused on identifying when the resin viscosity reaches a minimum during the initial temperature ramp. We also use direct ultrasonic measurements to monitor the efficiency of the part consolidation process and, subsequently, cross link formation in the matrix. The control strategy uses current information on temperature and pressure along with the ultrasonic property information as inputs into the cure process model and periodically evaluates alternative strategies to identify the optimum temperature and pressure profiles to use. This process can be continued in an iterative fashion until the part is fully cured. The result is a process control method that takes optimal advantage of nondestructive characterization and process modeling capabilities.

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, there has been dramatic growth in the utilization of polymer-based composites for a wide variety of applications. Advanced polymeric matrix composite materials, with high specific strength and stiffness, have enabled substantial technical performance advances in both airframe and aircraft engine applications. Moreover, the research and development of new polymeric composites for higher temperature applications have been remarkably successful, and these new generation materials, with improved toughness and thermal properties, are now entering the prototype component manufacturing and evaluation phase.

There are several major factors which currently limit the more widespread application and faster growth of composite materials in the manufacturing industry. Prominent among these factors, is the fact that processing of advanced composite materials is still mostly a skill/craft-type of activity. Most of the material systems are chemically reactive with multiple reaction pathways so that variation in stoichiometry, temperature-time history, and material process parameters significantly affect the precise distribution of molecular products and consequently the molecular microstructure of a final part. Processing decisions are routinely made on a highly qualitative *ad*

hoc basis with a "cut and try" philosophy being prevalent. Such an approach leads to long cycle times for process evaluation at the prototype stage, and to highly variable and unpredictable yields and high cost in manufacturing. These problems are further exacerbated in the newer and higher performance materials which are, in general, subject to more hostile physical processing environments and which require more stringent control of the manufacturing process.

A great deal of research effort has been expended in the study of the composite fabrication process, particularly as it applies to the fabrication of high performance composite laminates by autoclave curing. A number of researchers have worked on the fabrication and modeling issues, including Springer [1], Kardos et al. [2], and Gutowski [3-4]. However, the development of suitable process control strategies is still in its formative stages. The complexity of the fabrication process makes it challenging to develop an optimal strategy for process control. Many of the objectives in the composite manufacturing process depend on changes in resin properties either via transport through the composite or through the crosslinking reaction. It is desired to produce a void-free laminate, fully crosslinked with the maximum fiber volume fraction possible. Gases, either entrained during lay-up or evolved during cure, must be removed to prevent void formation and excess porosity. Additionally, maximal ply consolidation is sought. Both of these objectives are best achieved when resin viscosity, hence resistance to flow, is a minimum. This is the optimal time for pressurization within the autoclave. For most practical resin systems in current use the viscosity will initially decrease (from its B stage values) with increasing temperature, reach a minimum and increase monotonically thereafter as crosslink density increases. Heretofore, this behavior is built into the recommended cure cycle and considerable errors are involved in determining the best time for autoclave pressurization. In this research, we attempt to improve this situation via in-situ measurements of resin properties.

A variety of methods have been suggested for resin characterization during cure. Dielectric property measurements, which are sensitive to ionic mobility within the resin, have been studied for this purpose. These results are then correlated with viscosity using mathematical models for this relationship. One of the major shortcomings of this approach is that instead of absolute property values only relative property changes can be reliably measured. Ultrasonic measurements are another alternative to this approach. Since the initial work of Dietz et al., in 1952 [5], the potential for quantitative characterization of the changes in the rheological properties of polymer resins during cure has been extensively studied [5-8]. In general, these methods are nondestructive, rapid and highly sensitive. In the relatively simple case of a linearly elastic medium, ultrasonic techniques are based upon the relationships which exist between acoustic velocities and elastic moduli. Hence, accurate measurement of velocity results in determination of moduli if the density is known. For viscoelastic media, the relationships between acoustic and elastic properties are somewhat more complex, but the basics are much the same. In our research program ultrasonic techniques are used directly to measure the mechanical properties of the composite curing time. These measurements serve as primary inputs into the decision making strategy for process control.

2. ULTRASONIC CHARACTERIZATION

The constitutive equations for a linearly viscoelastic medium (given here for shear) are of the form

$$\tau_{xy}(t) = \int_{-\infty}^t \mu(t-t') \dot{\gamma}_{xy}(t') dt' \quad (1)$$

where τ_{xy} = shear stress
 γ_{xy} = shear strain

μ = viscoelastic modulus

For harmonic motions $\gamma_{xy}(t) = \gamma_0 \sin \omega t$, the shear stress is determined to be

$$\tau(t) = \int_{-\infty}^t \mu(t-t') \omega \gamma_0 \cos \omega t' dt' \quad (2)$$

Employing the substitution $s = t - t'$, Eq. (2) can be written in the form

$$\tau(t) = \gamma_0 [\mu'(\omega) \sin \omega t + \mu''(\omega) \cos \omega t] \quad (3)$$

where

$$\mu'(\omega) = \omega \int_0^{\infty} \mu(s) \sin \omega s ds$$

$$\mu''(\omega) = \omega \int_0^{\infty} \mu(s) \cos \omega s ds$$

Similar expressions can be derived for the remaining stress components.

Accordingly, for harmonic wave propagation in viscoelastic media, the (shear) wave equation becomes for a single frequency

$$\mu^* \nabla^2 \underline{u} = \rho \frac{\partial^2 \underline{u}}{\partial t^2} \quad (4)$$

where ρ = density
 \underline{u} = displacement

$$\mu^* = \mu' + i \mu''$$

For longitudinal wave propagation, the wave equation becomes

$$[\gamma^* + 2\mu^*] \nabla^2 \underline{u} = \rho \frac{\partial^2 \underline{u}}{\partial t^2} \quad (5)$$

For plane wave propagation (along the x axis), the solutions to wave equations are of the form

$$\underline{u}(x,t) = \underline{A} e^{i(kx - \omega t)} \quad (6)$$

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Neat Resin

In order to be useful for cure monitoring purposes, it must be demonstrated that ultrasonic test techniques are sensitive to changes in: a) viscosity and b) degree of cure of the resin. One of the principal objectives of this study was to evaluate the utility of ultrasonic testing in these two areas.

First, let us consider shear behavior. Figure 1a shows the real part (storage) of the shear modulus vs. time profile for neat resin samples (Fiberite 934 Epoxy) tested at these different heat rates in the rheometer. Figure 1b shows equivalent plot for the ultrasonic tests. Clearly, although there are some differences between the two curves as is expected due to the large difference (six orders of magnitude) in frequencies of the two test methods, the minimum in resin viscosity is clearly identifiable in all tests and occur at the same time in both the low frequency (rheometer) and high frequency (ultrasonic) tests.

Fig. (1a) Storage Modulus Profile. Heat rate = 7.2 °F/min (Rheometer).

Fig. (1b) Storage Modulus (C_{66}). Heat rate = 7.2 °F/min. (Ultrasonic).

The crosslinking reaction was also studied via differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and ultrasonic testing. Typical DSC output is presented in Figure 2. The heat evolved by a sample

Fig. (2) Ultrasonic profile and DSC plot. Heat rate = 7.2 °F/min.

can be used as a measure of the degree of cure, α , of the resin via the relation

$$\alpha(t) = \frac{\int_0^t \frac{1}{\rho} \left(\frac{dq}{dt} \right) dt}{\int_0^{t_f} \frac{1}{\rho} \left(\frac{dq}{dt} \right) dt} \quad (7)$$

where t_f is the time for complete reaction and dq/dt is the rate of heat generation from the curing process. It should be noted that the denominator in Equation (7) represents the total heat of reaction, H_r , for the complete curing. To utilize thermomechanical models during the curing process of thermosetting composites, the amount of heat generation rate needs to be specified as a function of time. Therefore, using the definition given in Equation (7), the rate of heat generation, dq/dt , can be expressed as

$$\frac{dq}{dt} = \rho H_r \frac{d\alpha}{dt} \quad (8)$$

Hence, predictive ability of thermochemical cure models can be utilized real time if one can obtain the time dependent evolution of degree of cure during the curing inside the autoclave.

From this viewpoint, the ultrasonic data can be simply used as an independent measure of the degree of cure. Considering that the ultrasonic data provide a measure of sample stiffness, one can suggest the following expression for the degree of cure

$$\alpha(t) = \frac{E_m(t) - E_m^{\circ}}{E_m^{\infty} - E_m^{\circ}} \quad (9)$$

where E_m° and E_m^{∞} are the initial and fully-cured stiffness values, and $E_m(t)$ is the time dependent data obtained from ultrasonic testing. Figure 3 shows a comparison of degree of cure results obtained for three different heat rates. Relatively good agreement is observed between two different ways of calculating degree of cure. Of course, during the early stages of the curing process, the stiffness of the material decreases due to melting of the resin. This is depicted in Figure 3 by the data obtained from ultrasonic testing as degree of cure obtained from Equation (9) initially yields negative values.

Fig. (3a) Comparison of degree of cure obtained from ultrasonic testing and DSC data. Heat rate = 7°F/min; $T_{\max} = 350^{\circ}\text{F}$; best fit obtained for $\gamma = 0.5$.

Fig. (3b) Comparison of degree of cure obtained from ultrasonic testing and DSC data. Heat rate = 9°F/min; $T_{\max} = 350^{\circ}\text{F}$; best fit obtained for $\gamma = 0$.

Fig. (3c) Comparison of degree of cure obtained from ultrasonic testing and DSC data. Heat rate = 10.8°F/min; best fit obtained for $\gamma = -0.5$.

However, during these early steps of the curing process, the reactions in the resin do not start which yield a zero degree of cure based on Equation (7). Consequently, the degree of cures defined in Equation (7) and in Equation (9) can be compared or correlated with each other only after the degree of cure obtained from ultrasonic testing is greater than zero. The correlation between the ultrasonic data and DSC results can be improved significantly if the following extension is implemented

$$\frac{E_m(t) - E_m^{\circ}}{E_m^{\infty} - E_m^{\circ}} = \alpha + \gamma [1 - \alpha] \alpha \quad (10)$$

where γ is a fitting parameter. Following Equation (10), values of the fitting parameter γ is determined for the best fit to degree of cure obtained from DSC data. For the three different heat rates considered, the value of the γ is found to be between -0.5 and 0.5. In fact, for high heating rates DSC data leads the ultrasonic data whereas for low heating rates DSC data lags behind the ultrasonic readings. Therefore, one may expect that the fitting parameter γ is a function of heating rates. Furthermore, it is observed from Figure 3 that if ultrasonic data leads DSC data then $\gamma > 0$, and if DSC data leads the ultrasonic data then $\gamma < 0$.

3.2 Fiber Reinforced Composites

Based on the neat resin results, we then turned our attention to filled resin samples to verify that similar results could be obtained even though the presence of reinforcing fiber changes the analysis since fibers produce a significant stiffening of the matrix, even in the through thickness direction. Since individual fiber properties do not change appreciably during processing, one might expect to see the same change in response, but not necessarily to the same degree. Furthermore, the sensitivity of ultrasonic test procedure to changes in material properties during consolidation was also of intent.

Typical ultrasonic test results for the behavior of the composite samples during cure are presented in Figure 4 for the test cycles described previously for a) longitudinal (velocity) and b) longitudinal (amplitude). Remembering that the velocity is a measure of modulus/density, let us first consider the behavior of the longitudinal velocity. The general trend in the longitudinal velocity data is for the velocity to decrease initially to a minimum value at the gel point, increase rapidly during cross-linking and stabilize for the balance of the test. For longitudinal wave propagation, the amplitude decreases rapidly in the beginning of the test as the gel point is reached and increases during the solidification of the resin.

If we compare the results for the three different soak temperatures, notice that in the initial stages of the test some variability in material behavior is observed, probably due to differences in the initial staging of the material. We also find that crosslinking occurs in a very narrow time range of approximately 20-25 minutes period after which little change in material properties is observed. Clearly, the extent of crosslinking is significantly reduced for this resin at the lower soak temperature which results in diminished properties in the cured samples. We also investigated the effect of heating rate on cure. In our work, the stiffness of the final part was optimized at a heating rate of approximately 4.5° F/min. Reducing or increasing this rate resulted in diminishing the efficiency of the crosslinking process and, therefore, a reduction in mechanical properties.

In comparison, the filled composite to the neat resin, we would expect the unfilled resin system to exhibit a lower stiffness than the filled system at comparable temperatures. Note that this is not observed for the pregelation portion of the test. This indicates that our neat resin samples were overstaged; hence the initial reading was not consistent with our expectation. Nonetheless, these readings show that the temperature where the minimum viscosity is achieved is readily identifiable from the ultrasonic velocity data.

Fig. (4a) Velocity (L) vs. time.

Fig. (4b) Amplitude (L) vs. time.

Another critical area of concern in cure monitoring is the behavior of the composite during consolidation. To examine this further, we performed a set of experiments at three different pressures in the autoclave (0 psi, 15 psi and 30 psi) during soak. Results are shown in Figure 5. As expected, increasing the applied pressure enhances the resin flow, thus reducing the void content and increasing the fiber volume fraction in the cured laminate.

To illustrate the use of this approach, we deliberately introduced an undercure condition in the laminate with a 250° F soak instead of 350° F as shown in Figure 6. Ultrasonic test results clearly show the disparity between the ideal response at 350° and the undercure response. Based on this discrepancy, undercure was recognized and the autoclave temperature was adjusted to the proper value at t=5000 seconds. The ultrasonic data clearly show that the ability to recognize and correct this cure error produced a final part with a velocity, hence stiffness, comparable to that of the ideal 350° F cure specimen.

Fig. (5) Effect of pressure on velocity.

Fig. (6) Effect of temperature compensation during cure cycle.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, an ultrasonic technique for directly monitoring the autoclave cure of composite laminates (*in situ* and in real-time) has been demonstrated. The approach is based on direct velocity measurements using high temperature ultrasonic transducers bonded to the tool plate. In particular, we have shown that ultrasonic velocity measurements can be used to:

- Track the reduction in resin viscosity at the outset of the test to insure that the viscosity has been reduced sufficiently for efficient resin transport.
- Monitor the consolidation process so that porosity has been reduced to acceptable levels and excess resins has been removed from the sample.
- Directly determine the degree of cure in the sample by measuring the increase in sample stiffness associated with crosslinking.

Further, we have indicated how this approach can be used for process control using ultrasonic measurements to identify a specific problem and correct it via suitable compensation. We believe that this type of approach will significantly improve the autoclave cure processing of composites.

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